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The Intrinsic Function of the Globus Pallidus Externus

In Silico

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Funktionen hos Globus Pallidus Externus – *In Silico*

Bakgrund: Att välja rätt handling i en miljö i ständig förändring är en kritisk funktion för nervsystemet. De basala ganglierna, en grupp subkortikala nervkärnor, spelar en central roll i den här processen genom deras förmåga att koordinera aktiviteten i nätverk på olika nivåer av nervsystemet. Dysfunktion i det här systemet associeras med, exempelvis, Parkinsons sjukdom, Huntingtons sjukdom och schizofreni. Nya rön visar att globus pallidus externus (GPe) har en avgörande betydelse för de basala gangliernas aktivitet men dess *modus operandi* har inte klarlagts. *Syfte:* Det här arbetet syftade till att rekonstruera globus pallidus externus som en biofysiskt detaljerad modell där dess huvudsakliga neuronpopulationer, deras synaptiska interaktioner och interaktion med striatum finns representerade. *Material och Metoder:* En modell av GPe konstruerades utifrån elektrofysiologisk, morfologisk och konnektivitetsrelaterad data. Cellerna representerades som multikompartmentella konduktansmodeller, deras synaptiska interaktion med Tsodyks-Markram-formalism, och deras konnektivitet utifrån spatial närhet. *Resultat:* Den modellerade cellpopulationen var statistiskt representativ för dess biologiska motpart, inklusive för data som ej använts vid parameterjustering ($p=1.000$). Cellmodellerna inkorporerades i ett nätverk bestående av 10 000 neuroner och deras interaktion med striatum kunde studeras. Spatiotemporalt korrelerade subthalamiska signaler kunde effektivt driva aktiviteten i GPe. Den här aktiviteten var tillräcklig för att kunna inhibera kortikala signaler till striatum. *Slutsats:* Modellen replikerar inkluderade data med statistisk säkerhet. Preliminära simuleringar indikerar att GPe responderar till spatiotemporalt strukturerade signaler, vilket antyder att det finns ett biologiskt realistiskt signaleringssystem utanför den klassiska modellen för de basala gangliernas funktion.

The Intrinsic Function of the Globus Pallidus Externus – *In Silico*

Introduction: Choosing the appropriate action in response to an ever-changing environment presents a major challenge for the nervous system. The basal ganglia, a group of subcortical nuclei, play a central role in this process by coordinating the activity of networks at different levels of the nervous system. Dysfunction of these is associated with, for example, Parkinson's disease, Huntington's disease, and schizophrenia. Emerging evidence shows that the globus pallidus externus (GPe) significantly affects basal ganglia activity. Its *modus operandi*, however, remains unknown. *Aims:* This work aimed to reconstruct the GPe microcircuit as a biophysically detailed model, representing its main neuronal populations, their synaptic dynamics, and the interaction with striatum. *Material and Methods:* A model of the GPe was constructed based on electrophysiological, morphological and connectivity data. The cells were represented as multicompartimental conductance models, their synaptic interaction by Tsodyks-Markram formalism, and the connectivity by using a touch detection algorithm. *Results:* The modelled cell population was statistically indistinguishable from its biological counterpart, including out-of-sample datasets ($p=1.000$). The cell models were incorporated into a network consisting of 10 000 neurons and their interaction with striatum was studied. Spatiotemporally clustered subthalamic inputs effectively drove GPe activity. This activity was sufficient to inhibit cortical signals to the striatum. *Conclusions:* The model accurately replicates the included data with statistical certainty. Preliminary simulations indicates that the GPe responds to spatiotemporally structured signals, suggesting that there is a biologically plausible mode of signaling which does not conform to the classical model of basal ganglia function.

Keywords: Globus pallidus externus, action selection, basal ganglia, Parkinson's disease, dyskinesia, computational analysis

Abbreviations

AIS	Axon initial segment
AP	Action potential
bAP	Backpropagating action potential
dAP	Dendritic action potential
GPe	Globus pallidus externus
GPi	Globus pallidus internus
SNC	Substantia nigra pars compacta
SNr	Substantia nigra pars reticulata

Background

Action Selection and the Basal Ganglia

Choosing the appropriate action in response to an ever-changing environment presents a major challenge for the nervous system. This encompasses a wide range of behaviors, from simple reflexes to complex, goal-directed action. The context imposes different constraints upon these in terms of latency, coordination, and precision, all of which must be balanced by the nervous system to achieve a viable behavioral repertoire.

Motor functions are represented by a variety of dedicated, movement-specific neuronal networks, which are distributed at different levels of the nervous system, collectively termed a “*motor infrastructure*” (1). These, along with networks representing learned motor functions, form the basic components of complex motor behaviors. The forebrain, mainly the cortex and the basal ganglia, coordinates the activity of these (2). Their respective roles are complex, but as evident from ablation and lesioning studies in several species, the basal ganglia are necessary for adaptive behavior while the cortex is not (2,3).

The basal ganglia are involved in a variety of neural functions, including control of movement, procedural learning, executive function, and processing of emotions (2,4,5). It is, therefore, not surprising that disorders of the basal ganglia can result in a variety of disease manifestations. These include Parkinson’s disease and Huntington’s disease, as well as several psychiatric conditions, including obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD), Tourette’s syndrome, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), and schizophrenia (2,4,6).

The Classical Model of Basal Ganglia Function

The basal ganglia are a group of subcortical nuclei (Fig. 1) involved in both motor and cognitive behaviors (2). Their output nuclei, the substantia nigra pars reticulata (SNr) and the globus pallidus internus (GPI), contain autonomously active GABAergic neurons which exert tonic inhibition on downstream motor centers so that cells in these need to be inhibited for movement to occur (2). The main input structure of the basal ganglia, the striatum, mainly consists of GABAergic projection neurons (SPNs), which make up 95% of the neuronal count, and a diverse set of interneurons (2). The SPNs can further be subdivided into at least two categories corresponding to two distinct pathways, the direct and the indirect pathways. SPNs of the direct pathway (dSPN) project mainly to the SNr and GPI, express dopamine D1 receptors, and release

substance P, while those of the indirect pathway (iSPN) project to the globus pallidus externus, express D2 receptors and release enkephalin (2). The remaining striatal neurons are composed of several types of interneurons (2). Neurons of the other basal ganglia nuclei are GABAergic and autonomously active except for the subthalamic nucleus (STN), which uses glutamate (2,4,6).

The most prevalent model of the basal ganglia posits that the direct and indirect pathways serve to facilitate and inhibit movement, respectively (5,7,8). Dopamine exerts opposing effects on the two pathways, increasing the firing rate of the direct pathway while decreasing it for the indirect pathway (5,8). In the classical model, the output of the basal ganglia is governed by the firing rate of neurons in the respective pathways, referred to as a “rate model” (8). The selected action is thus the one having the cellular representation with the highest firing rate. However, there is evidence that both pathways are concomitantly active during natural behaviors (9).

Figure 1. The Main Pathways of the Basal Ganglia. The output nuclei, the substantia nigra pars reticulata (SNr) and the globus pallidus internus (GPi), project to subpopulations of neurons in the superior colliculus (SC), the mesencephalic locomotor region (MLR), and diencephalic locomotor region (DLR), and other brainstem motor centers, as well as the thalamus and the brainstem. The striatal projection neurons (dSPNs) express the dopamine D1 receptor (D1) and targets the output nuclei, while the iSPNs express D2 and target the globus pallidus externus (GPe). The GPe is reciprocally connected with the striatum. Adapted from (2), courtesy of Sten Grillner.

While the classical model is based on a much-simplified view of the circuitry, it has nevertheless been useful for investigating basal ganglia function. For example, optogenetic activation of the direct and indirect pathways induces opposing effects on motor behavior, as expected from the rate model (10). However, in patients and animal models of Parkinson's disease, only modest changes in firing rate are observed, which is not expected from the rate model (4,5). Instead, there is a marked change in firing pattern as well as an increased correlation in activity between cells (4).

The Globus Pallidus Externus in Relation to the Classical Model

Traditionally, the GPe has been viewed as a nucleus that relays information from the striatum to the GPi, SNr, and STN as part of the indirect pathway in the classical model (5). Since then, there has been a growing body of evidence that is difficult to reconcile with this view, instead pointing to a more substantial role of the GPe in basal ganglia processing (1, 4, 5).

In the contemporary view, the GPe is composed of at least two cell types, differing in terms of their connectivity, electrophysiological behavior, and sensitivity to neurotransmitters and pharmacological agents. The most numerous of the two, the prototypic neurons, account for approximately 60-80% of the neuronal count and have projections to downstream targets but also the striatum (11,12). A smaller subpopulation, the arky pallidal neurons, projects solely to the striatum, and are marked by their massive axonal arborizations and numerous synapses. They have been suggested to function as “stop cells” because of their large number of inhibitory synapses in the striatum and that an increase in their firing rate is associated with the cancellation of imminent action in behavioral experiments (13,14). The arky pallidal neurons express the transcription factor Forkhead box protein 2 (FoxP2) and preproenkephalin (PPE), while the prototypical neurons express Nk2 homeobox 1 (Nkx2.1) or parvalbumin (PV), although a range of other markers is associated with specific projection patterns and electrophysiological traits (12,14–16). The arky pallidal neurons are preferentially inhibited by dSPNs while the prototypical neurons are mainly targeted by iSPNs, although there is some overlap between the pathways (17,18). Both cell types make synaptic connections within the GPe, the strongest being from the prototypic to the arky pallidal neurons (17–20). Interestingly, both arky pallidal and prototypic neurons express D2-receptors (6). Prototypic neurons also express the Substance P-sensitive Nk1r-receptor (21). Several other receptors are present in the GPe, e.g., adenosinergic, serotonergic, and cholinergic ones (6,22,23).

Results from studies in live animals also present a more nuanced role of the function of the GPe. Both optogenetic excitation and inhibition of the indirect pathway prevent the initiation of action sequences and abort ongoing ones (9). Similarly, during active locomotion, the firing rate of arky pallidal neurons increases (24), suggesting that the GPe actively modulates activity in the basal ganglia during natural behaviors. The significance of the cellular heterogeneity in the GPe has been demonstrated in an optogenetic study where selectively raising the activity of prototypical neurons expressing PV over those expressing Lhx6 restores movement in dopamine-depleted mice with effects lasting several hours after the cessation of stimulus (25).

Understanding the GPe Microcircuit

The activity of the GPe is determined by the dynamical interaction of a diverse set of cells, and intrinsic and extrinsic afferents (4,6,23). Understanding how these interact is difficult to do intuitively, since it involves an amount of data that is both intractably large and, simultaneously, incomplete. For other brain areas, such as the neocortex (26) and the striatum (27), this problem has been dealt with by reconstructing them *in silico*, i.e., as biophysical models whose activity can be simulated using computers (26,27).

As a concrete example, consider the activation of a single synapse: In a biophysically detailed model, the goal is that this elicits the same current response as that of its biological counterpart, in turn, causing the same change in membrane voltage in the target cell, activating the same set of (simulated) ion channels, and so on. In essence, the goal of these models is to capture the biophysical processes governing the function of the biological brain, the general idea being that the intrinsic function of the brain can be understood by analyzing the activity of its physical properties (26–30). While parts of the basal ganglia microcircuit, such as the striatum (27,31), have been modelled at a biophysically detailed level, no such model currently exists for the GPe.

Aims

This work aimed to reconstruct the GPe microcircuit as a biophysical model, with the overarching aim of understanding the intrinsic function of the GPe. Specifically, the microcircuit was reconstructed to have models of individual cell types, synapses and their dynamics, and networks of neurons with appropriate connectivity, so that the interaction between the GPe and the striatum could be simulated and analyzed.

Methods

Reconstruction of the GPe microcircuit was performed in several steps (26,27), initially by creating models of individual cell types based on electrophysiological data, then, by creating models of different types of synapses, and lastly, incorporating the modelled neurons and synapses into a network. In technical terms, a multicompartmental Hodgkin-Huxley-formalism was used for the cell models (26,27), Tsodyks-Markram-formalism for synaptic models (28), and a touch detection algorithm for network connectivity (27).

Models of Individual Cells

In order to create models of individual cells, their morphology was first reconstructed and then populated with ion channels set to levels which could replicate the membrane dynamics of their biological counterparts.

Reconstruction of Single Cell Morphologies

Single cell morphologies were reconstructed based on confocal images of biocytin filled (mouse) cells from an unpublished dataset shared by Dr. Linda Koene. Reconstructions were performed using NeuTube (32). A default assumption of tissue shrinkage of 10% in the XY-plane and 20% in the Z-plane were compensated for. The reconstructions were further postprocessed to account for contraction and resampled to a standardized compartment length of 5 μm (27). For compatibility with the framework employed for the network reconstruction, somata were represented as single-point spheres with the radii set to make the surface area match those of the original reconstructed morphologies (27).

Estimation of Active Membrane Properties

Electrophysiological models were based on *in vitro* patch-clamp recordings from mice at 35°C according to a previously established procedure (cf. (27)). These were matched with their corresponding morphological reconstruction; otherwise, a morphology of a neuron with similar input resistance was picked. Choice of active membrane properties and their subcellular distributions were based on the expression of channel markers from RNA-sequencing data (16), optical (33), voltage clamp and pharmacological studies (33,34), and prior theoretical work (23,29,30,35).

Estimation of Ionic Currents

Models of delayed rectifier currents were based on electrophysiological recordings of homomeric subunits using automated patch clamp at 35° from a publicly available dataset (36). Parameters for these were obtained by large-scale optimization, tuning to match their conductance-voltage relation, inactivation dynamics etc., using a custom-built procedure implemented in Python with NEURON and BluePyOpt (26). The sodium currents were modelled as a persistent and transient fraction based on prior experimental work (34). D-type and slowly inactivating, type-A currents were estimated from voltage clamp studies and modelled using an extended Hodgkin-Huxley formalism (37). The remaining currents, i.e., calcium-dependent potassium currents, calcium currents, inwards rectifier potassium currents (kir), hyperpolarization-activated cyclic nucleotide-gated (HCN) channels, and Kv4.2-currents were obtained from the literature (23,29,30,35). Exhaustive genealogy of each channel model was documented in their respective programmatic implementations. Temperatures were corrected for using Q10, with a default guess value of 5 for potassium channels and 3 for the remainder (26,27).

Parameter Tuning

The parameters of the cell models were tuned to match the electrophysiological behavior of their biological counterparts using a subset of the protocols available in the data. Fitness of the models were assessed by their ability to replicate relevant electrophysiological features, i.e., maximal rise rate, maximal fall rate, action potential (AP) peak, AP threshold (defined as the last crossing of 10 mV/ms before a maxima), current to firing rate relation, frequency adaptation and voltage sag. Simulated and experimental traces were upsampled to 200 kHz using cubic interpolation implemented in Scipy (38).

Tuning of the parameters was performed in several iterations, initially by tuning for subthreshold responses, then for the shape of the AP wave form and lastly frequency-current relation. Parameter tuning used a combination of manual tuning and large-scale optimization using BluePyOpt (26). The latter was mainly used for tuning specific traits, e.g., in sensitive regions of the parameter space. The parameters were constrained using a variety of experimental sources, e.g., the maximal conductance of ionic currents was constrained by estimates from voltage clamp studies and variability in channel dynamics based on electrophysiological studies of ion channels (34,36).

Models of Synapses and Their Dynamics

To be able to study the interaction between the cell models, models of different types of synapses were made.

Synaptic Dynamics

Synaptic dynamics were implemented using the (event-based) Tsodyks-Markram model (28) and tuned to match their biological counterparts (20,39,40). Synaptic models were based on digitized traces from the literature (27,39,40) or sometimes on parameters from the literature (31). Connection strengths were estimated based on bouton counts and unitary conductances (11,19,20,31).

Network Model of the Interaction Between the GPe and Striatum

To study the interaction between cell models, both within the GPe, and between the GPe and the striatum, the cell models and synapses were incorporated into a network.

Connectivity Estimation

The cell models were connected by first obtaining putative locations for synaptic contacts based on spatial appositions and selecting among these using a set of pruning rules (27). The connectivity within the GPe was estimated based on optogenetic studies as well anatomical stainings (17,19,20), obtaining a rough approximation of connection probabilities. Data from studies in rats were used in case mouse data were unavailable (6,18,19). The connectivity between the nuclei was mainly based on synaptic counts (11,19). Estimates for the striatal network are obtained from the literature (27). Synaptic dynamics and connectivity for inputs from the STN to the GPe are obtained from a previous modelling study (31).

Representations of Axonal Arborizations

Detailed axonal reconstructions were not available. These were therefore coarsely approximated by programmatically generating reconstructions based on rough estimates of their geometry, number of branches, branch lengths and total arborization length from the literature (11,19). The rationale for using this method is that it can accurately represent the total branch length thus being able to approximate conduction latencies between synapses in very large arbors.

Mapping Intranuclear Projections

Projections between the GPe and the Striatum were assumed to be somatotopically organized and evenly distributed throughout the nucleus (41). The placement of terminal fields was obtained by creating a coordinate mapping between the mesh representations of the nuclei using Blender (www.blender.org). These were then rotated by using a similar method of creating a mapping between the vertices and the normals (or negative normals) of the meshes. These maps were then used in Snudda, although with a custom extension to allow for using reconstructed axonal arbors and establishing rotations based on the coordinate of the source cell in some cases.

Simulation and Analysis of the Model

The network model was simulated using the NEURON simulation environment and Snudda (26,27).

Statistics

The accuracy of the cell models was verified by comparing their electrophysiological responses to their biological counterparts. Cells were initially checked manually during the parameter tuning stage. To verify that the model was statistically representative of the biological system, the complete population of model neurons were compared to its experimental counterpart using a Mann-Whitney U-test implemented in Scipy (38). A cutoff of $p < 0.05$ was used for significance testing along with a Bonferroni adjustment for multiple comparisons.

Ethical Considerations

All experimental data used in this work have been collected by other groups – collected for other studies – under their respective ethical permits and are used herein with their permission.

An essential aspect of ethical animal experiments is to maximize the utility of the data already available. Theoretical studies allow for the creation of more exact formulations of and better stratification among hypotheses, thus increasing the likelihood of performing accurate experiments with minimal waste, thus reducing the number of animal experiments needed to address a question. The ethical risks with this work are therefore minimal since no additional animals needed to be harmed in the process, and the benefits, therefore, come at practically zero ethical cost.

Results

Models of Individual Cells

Multicompartmental, Hodgkin-Huxley models were built based on recordings from neurons expressing parvalbumin (PV) (n=5) and Forkhead box protein 2 (FoxP2) (n=2). An extensive set of ionic currents known to be present in the GPe were included in the model; among them, the fast and persistent sodium currents (12,34,42), the delayed rectifier currents (Kv2.1, Kv3.1/Kv3.2) (30,43), a fast inactivating type A current (Kv4.2) (30,43), a slowly inactivating type A current (37,44), a D-type current (37,44), a range of calcium currents (P/Q-, R-, N-, and L-types) (27,30), calcium-dependent potassium currents (SK2, BK) (27,30,45), and hyperpolarization-activated cyclic nucleotide-activated currents (HCN1, HCN2) (46). These were distributed differently over the somatodendritic extent based on known expression patterns, results from optical methods and earlier theoretical works (29,30,33,42).

This resulted in a population of cell models, all of which could replicate the electrophysiological behavior of their biological counterparts, i.e., the subthreshold responses, action potential waveform, and spiking events, (Table 1). Representative traces of single action potential waveforms are shown in Fig. 2B and 3B for PV- and FoxP2-expressing cells, respectively, and responses to current injections in Fig. 2C and 3C. At the population level, the modelled population was statistically indistinguishable from the experimental one (Table 1), including out-of-sample protocols (Table 1, underscored columns). The out-of-sample protocols were assessed by the subthreshold steady-state-voltage response to current injections (approximately 10 protocols per neuron) and firing rate at suprathreshold current injections (9 protocols per neuron), with the model and experimental populations being statistically identical for the included metrics ($p=1.000$ and $p=1.000$, respectively).

The magnitude of ionic currents approximated that of the available experimental literature. Effects of blocking SK- and BK-channels were similar to those in the literature. Blockage of SK channels for the models of PV neurons yielded a 28.6% increase in firing rate at driven rates (~60Hz), similar to the ~25% observed in rats (47) from similar firing rates. In FoxP2 neurons, blockage of BK-channels yielded a 43% decrease in firing rate, close to the 30% observed in the mouse (45) from resting rates (~5Hz).

Table 1. Electrophysiological Features of the Model

Electrophysiological traits of the cell models (bold numbers) and their biological counterparts (non-bold). Underscored headings are out-of-sample protocols. The final row designates the (unadjusted) P-values of the Mann-Whitney U-test for each metric.

<i>Cell ID</i>	Trough	Steady State	<u>IV</u>	AP Peak	AHP	AP Thr.	Maximal Rise Rate	Maximal Fall Rate	Spike Count	Spike Count (low)	Spike Count (high)	Spike Count Adaptation	<u>Rate / Current Step</u>
Unit	mV	mV	<u>mV/pA</u>	mV	mV	mV	V/s	V/s	1	1	1	1	<u>Hz/pA</u>
FoxP2-1	-99.0	-97.3	0.392	2.68	-68.9	-50.8	316	-103	3	40	57	1.00	0.673
	-96.7	-94.0	0.457	-0.24	-68.0	-46.8	190	-117	4	37	55	-	0.769
FoxP2-2	-113.7	-109.2	0.197	-0.10	-64.4	-44.8	329	-131	10	68	103	0.25	0.465
	-113.9	-105.4	0.189	-1.47	-62.0	-44.6	203	-131	11	60	88	0.40	0.365
PV-1	-95.1	-93.4	0.114	-10.5	-72.6	-56.8	405	-112	19	79	118	0.80	0.543
	-94.0	-92.3	0.113	-10.4	-70.2	-57.5	288	-184	13	49	123	0.75	0.747
PV-2	-95.8	-93.8	0.082	-2.66	-73.2	-53.9	379	-237	7	50	133	1.00	0.469
	-96.2	-94.3	0.089	1.60	-73.9	-54.7	373	-274	7	49	132	0.00	0.492
PV-3	-106	-102.1	0.153	-9.30	-69.5	-55.0	327	-137	11	-	-	0.50	-
	-104	-102.1	0.160	-14.0	-70.0	-56.9	268	-155	12	-	-	1.00	-
PV-4	-97	-95.7	0.247	-12.1	-75.5	-51.1	173	-101	7	40	84	1.00	0.605
	-98	-95.6	0.242	-6.29	-73.1	-54.6	266	-153	5	25	52	1.00	0.396
PV-5	-85.3	-83.8	0.259	-7.27	-78.5	-54.2	294	-102	5	-	-	1.00	-
	-84.4	-83.2	0.278	-10.4	-76.8	-56.9	299	-198	6	-	-	0.50	-
P =	0.902	0.710	1.000	1.000	0.805	0.383	0.128	0.073	1.000	0.293	0.690	0.367	1.000

Abbreviations: AP = action potential, AHP = after hyperpolarization, AP Thr. = AP threshold.

Figure 2. Model of parvalbumin (PV) expressing cell fitted to recordings from the globus pallidus externus (GPe). Experimental traces are in red, simulated in black. (A) Morphological reconstruction of a single prototypical neuron. (B) First action potential of the simulated and experimental traces superimposed. (C) Somatic action potentials in response to square-pulse current injections for 1 second. (D) Subthreshold membrane activity of the PV population under current injections. (E) Firing rate of the PV population under current injections.

Figure 3. Model of Forkhead Box Protein 2 (FoxP2) expressing cell fitted to recordings from the globus pallidus externus (GPe). Experimental traces are in red, simulated in black. (A) Morphology used for the FoxP2 neuron in B-E. (B) First action potential of the simulated and experimental traces superimposed. (C) Somatic response to square-pulse current injections for 1 second. (D) Subthreshold membrane activity of the FoxP2 population under current injections. (E) Firing rate of the FoxP2 population under current injections.

Models of Synapses and Their Dynamics

Active Dendritic Properties

Earlier experimental and theoretical work have shown that dendritic sodium currents are essential for the integration of synaptic events in the rat GPe through their role in the generation of dendritic action potentials (29,42). The cell models were therefore constructed with a dendritic sodium current density close to that in the soma, of approximately $1\text{E-}3$ to $1\text{E-}2$ S/cm² which is similar to that in other cell types with dendritic action potentials (48) but lower than that estimated in the rat GPe (42).

In the model, action potentials were initiated in the axon initial segment during normal pace making (Fig. 4A). Subthreshold synaptic events in the distal dendrites, furthermore, did not propagate to the soma (Fig. 4B, left) while suprathreshold could elicit a dendritic action potential and subsequently a somatic action potential (Fig. 4B, right). Subthreshold stimuli consisted of 5 subthalamic AMPA synapses (parameters from (31)) located 250 μm away from the soma and spatially clustered within 50 μm , activated at 40Hz. Suprathreshold activity was achieved using 25 synapses, the other parameters being the same.

Figure 4. Action Potential Propagation in the Model. (A) Antidromic AP propagation during somatic depolarization. (B) Dendritic spike initiation in GPe neurons. Subthreshold stimulation (5 STN synapses at 40Hz, left) yielded a subthreshold response which attenuated completely while suprathreshold stimulation (25 STN synapses at 40Hz, right) elicited a dendritic action potential which propagates to the soma.

Synaptic Interactions and Connectivity

To study how the cell models would interact at the network level, a network model was built using Snudda, a previously employed touch detection algorithm (27). The GPe is characterized by having sparse recurrent connectivity within the nucleus while having projections to all other basal ganglia nuclei (6,17–20,39,40). In the model, connections within the GPe and between the GPe and the striatum are represented (Fig. 5A, 5B) using the striatal model from (27).

The synaptic dynamics were modelled using the Tsodyks-Markram formalism with parameters tuned to match digitized traces from the literature (39,40). The modelled synapses recapitulate the main features of their biological counterparts, i.e., the facilitating or depressing dynamics, and the rise and fall rates (Fig. 5C-E).

Figure 5. The Modelled Connectivity Between the GPe and the Striatum. (A) Connection scheme between the striatum and the globus pallidus externus. The projection from parvalbumin (PV) to expressing GPe neurons and fast spiking interneurons (FS) striatal neurons is omitted from the model. (B) A single arbor of an FoxP21 neuron (black) encompasses a large area in the striatum, SPNs (blue and purple) shown for scale. (C) Synaptic dynamics from spiny projection neurons (SPNs) onto GPe neurons, based on data from (39). (D) Synaptic dynamics of the recurrent connectivity within the GPe, based on (40). (E) FoxP2 inputs onto the striatal neurons, based on (39).

Network Model of the Interaction Between the GPe and Striatum

Network Activity in the Model

To assess the ability of the GPe to inhibit the striatum, a reduced network model was built consisting of only SPNs. These were given a combination of cortical and thalamic background noise, and a short cortical signal intended to drive these neurons to high firing rates using parameters from (27). This procedure was then repeated with concurrent activation of the GPe synapses with the cortical signal, approximately 30 synapses from FoxP2 neurons driven at 40 Hz which is less than the maximal expected synapses onto SPNs (19). In this model, activation of the FoxP2 synapses effectively suppressed the rate increase associated with the cortical signal (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Inhibitory efficacy of FoxP2 synapses striatal spiny projection neurons (SPNs). Activation of the cortical (CTX) signal could effectively drive activity of the SPNs (green) but this effect could be terminated by concurrent activation of FoxP2 synapses (orange).

Large Scale Simulations

A network model consisting of approximately ~10 000 striatal neurons and ~100 GPe neurons was constructed to further explore the efficacy of the pallidostriatal connectivity, a similar network size to what has been used in other studies (27). The network was implemented using the circuit in Fig. 5A with cortical, thalamic and subthalamic background activity fed into the circuit. Upon activation of the subthalamic inputs, there is a marked increase in the rate in the GPe and a subsequent decrease in activity in the striatum (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. Large scale network simulation. Activation of inputs from the subthalamic nucleus (STN, in orange) effectively raised the firing rate of the globus pallidus externus (GPe, purple) resulting in inhibition of the striatum (purple).

Discussion

Action selection is a critical feature of the nervous system. Central to this process is a group of subcortical nuclei called the basal ganglia. Emerging evidence indicates that the globus pallidus externus (GPe) can significantly affect the activity of the basal ganglia, yet its mode of operation remains unknown (6,13,17,25,49). This work presents a biophysical reconstruction of the globus pallidus externus, including its main neuronal populations, their synaptic interaction, and the interaction between the GPe and the striatum. This model is the first, to the author's knowledge, to include the contemporary understanding of the GPe circuit at a biophysically detailed scale and its interaction with the striatum.

Model Verification

The model can be viewed as a composition of models of various aspects of the circuit, be it cells, synapses, or the spatial structure of the nuclei. The modelled cell population imitated its biological counterpart with sufficient accuracy, to the extent that they were statistically indistinguishable, out-of-sample protocols included. The synaptic models could replicate the dynamical features of their biological counterparts, but because of limited data, only qualitative comparisons were made. The data regarding the connectivity of the GPe is limited. The emerging view is that it is rather diverse, with several projections of the GPe targeting the striatum (13,18,19,40) along with local interactions within the GPe (17–19,39). The connectivity was therefore set up using a previously employed touch detection algorithm, Snudda (27), which constrains synaptic coupling to appositions between the cell models and limits the synaptic density to realistic (spatially attainable) values.

Cells of the GPe have previously been modelled at a biophysically detailed level in several studies (29,30,34). Compared to these, this model presents a more extensive and representative range of ion channels based on data which were not previously available. This includes RNA-sequencing data (16) to identify which channel proteins are expressed in the GPe, a large-scale voltage clamp study of homomeric ion channels (36) which allowed for more accurate channel kinetics (at physiological temperatures), and pharmacological studies (43,45,47) which probes the effect of single channel types for neuron activity. These data constrain which active membrane mechanisms are available for the cell models. By having included these, the model presented herein does not only display correct behaviors but also does so by using more realistic mechanisms.

Network Effects

The cell models could realistically portray the behavior of their biological counterparts. These were therefore integrated into a network model where their synaptic interactions could be studied. The modelled cells had been constructed to have dendrites with active properties, similar to those in the rat (29,42). This allowed a small set of spatiotemporally clustered subthalamic inputs to effectively drive the GPe circuit, and this activity was sufficient for effective striatal inhibition during cortical signals. This suggests that spatiotemporally correlated inputs can have pronounced effects on basal ganglia activity at large, with reservations for the uncertainties in the network connectivity. The effect did, however, persist between network simulations, i.e., the results from the small-scale simulations were comparable to those in the large-scale simulation, even though the inputs were not identical and there were differences in connectivity etc. It is interesting to note that this effect appears to not conform to the classical model of basal ganglia function, suggesting that the activity of the basal ganglia is not entirely determined by rate coding.

Strengths and Limitations

The brain is a notoriously complex system. With its vast amount of interacting components, understanding it intuitively is difficult. Computational models are therefore an important tool for analyzing how the nervous system functions. Biophysically detailed models, like the one presented herein, exist at the intersection of subcellular processes and network dynamics. This high level of detail can make the models opaque and difficult to work with. This imposes limits on the scale of the system to be studied since the computational cost of simulating these models is relatively high. One of their main benefits is that they can relate structure to function. For example, single ionic processes located in the periphery of a cell can be quantitatively studied with theoretical transparency and the full state of the model can be closely monitored during the course of a simulation.

Two limitations are particularly evident in this work. The first concerns active dendritic mechanisms in the GPe. Most electrophysiological characterizations of neurons revolves around the soma, in part due to technical limitations. However, in a combined modelling and experimental study, Hanson et al. (42) has shown that the dendrites of GPe neurons in the rat contain sodium channels at levels sufficient to initiate action potentials, thus profoundly affecting synaptic integration (42). Consistent with this, in the model presented herein, dendritic

sodium channels are involved in the same non-linear amplification of synaptic inputs. It is clear that active dendrites are likely to play a central role in basal ganglia functioning, seeing as inputs would otherwise attenuate almost completely before reaching the soma. However, what features they are equipped with is unknown and difficult to measure directly. These uncertainties leave open the possibility that synaptic integration in the GPe display even richer dynamics.

A second important limitation is the difficulty in constraining network connectivity. This stems from single parameters, e.g., unitary conductances or connection strengths, being difficult to measure directly. The indirect measurements, e.g., activation of fiber tracts, imposes uncertainties in terms of how many synapses are activated, where they are located in relation to the soma, etc., in essence meaning that several parameters must be tuned for simultaneously. This limits the generalizability of the effects observed at the network level, although some of this uncertainty is mitigated by comparing several instances of the model.

Significance

The basal ganglia have a fundamental role in the function and dysfunction of the nervous system, but there is no mechanistic description of how they operate. This work aimed to obtain a biophysical model of the globus pallidus externus, whose role in basal ganglia processing remains unclear. This model recapitulates findings from the experimental literature in an integration fashion, which allows for the analysis of their physiological role, the pathophysiological mechanisms underlying basal ganglia disorders, as well as identification of new therapeutic targets.

Equity

The organization of the basal ganglia are structurally similar for vertebrates in general (1,2), so studies at this fundamental level likely applies to a broad of demography.

Future Research

In the model, consistent with earlier theoretical and experimental works (29,42,47), active dendrites have a critical role in the integration of synaptic inputs and therefore basal ganglia information processing at large. Which active mechanisms are present in the dendrites of GPe neurons and if they differ at the level of neuronal subpopulations is unknown. The dendrites of

GPe neurons are notoriously long and thin which makes direct study of their activity difficult (42). By using a combination of computational and experimental methods, it may be possible to address this question using optical methods (e.g., electron microscopy or immunohistochemical methods) to identify which structural elements are present in the dendrites along with further subcellular specializations, and computational methods to investigate them quantitatively, specifically, by using optical methods to determine ion channel distribution at a subcellular level and computational methods to assess their integrated functional role.

A second difficult-to-constrain aspect of the model is its network dynamics. In recent years, there have been several electrophysiological investigations into intact networks by using optogenetic methods (17,18,25,49,50). These provide valuable insights into the dynamics of the intact network. Future theoretical studies should incorporate these findings. One key challenge in doing so is to develop theoretical constructs for systematically comparing these to the model, for example by modelling the action of channelrhodopsin directly.

Conclusions

This work presents a reconstruction of the GPe microcircuit as a biophysical model, accurately incorporating experimental findings from a range of modalities, from single ionic currents to interaction between nuclei. Based on the available data, the main cell populations can be modelled with sufficient accuracy to be statistically indistinguishable from their biological counterparts in terms of electrophysiology. The integration of synaptic input, however, critically depends on active membrane mechanisms in the distal dendrites, for which the data is limited. In the model, the active dendrites allow for a small number of spatially clustered synapses to effectively drive GPe activity. Moreover, a small number of FoxP2 neurons is sufficient to inhibit cortical signals to the striatum. This, with reservations for the preliminary nature of the network results, suggests that there is a biologically plausible mode of signaling which does not conform to the classical model of basal ganglia function.

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